

Assay of quinine sulfate and codeine phosphate in presence of each other

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Abstract : A simple and accurate spectrophotometric method has been developed for the assay of quinine sulfate and codeine phosphate simultaneously from a mixture of the two.

Keywords : Quinine sulphate, codeine phosphate.

As a modern trend, combinations of two or more drugs are frequently used for the treatment of diseases. Hence an analyst frequently encounters the situation when concentration of one drug is to be determined from such combined dosage forms. Spectrophotometric assay of such formulations involve the determination of absorbances of two or more components simultaneously from such preparations. The basis of spectrophotometric techniques for multi-component samples is that at all wavelengths, the absorbance of a solution is the sum of absorbances of the individual components^{1a}.

For a substance which obeys Beer's law at all wavelengths, the ratio of absorbances at any two wavelengths is constant and independent of concentration or pathlength, i.e. two different dilutions of the same substance gives the same absorbance ratio A_1/A_2 . This ratio is referred to as Q value^{1b}. British Pharmacopoeia use this ratio at specified wavelengths as confirmatory test for identity of different drug substances².

The present work involves two important antimalarial drugs quinine sulfate (Q.S.) and codeine phosphate (C.P.), which have a common λ_{\max} at 283.5 nm and hence determination of concentration of individual drugs from a mixture becomes difficult at 283.5 nm. Since quinine sulfate however, possess a second λ_{\max} at 331 nm, we attempted to follow the above stated principle and have successfully determined the individual concentration of the drugs from the mixture by measuring the absorbances of the mixtures at these two different λ_{\max} values.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of analytical grade and quinine sulfate and codeine phosphate were of I.P. grade. Spectrophotometric measurements were done in a UV/Vis spectrophotometer (Hitachi, Model No. UV2000). Double-distilled water (all glass) was used throughout.

Stock solution of C.P. and Q.S. of concentration 1 mg/ml were made with water. (pH adjusted to 2.3 with dil. H_2SO_4). Solutions of both the drugs were prepared separately having concentrations 24, 32, 40, 48 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, each being diluted from the stock solution with water. Four mixtures of the two drugs of equal concentrations (as stated above) were used for the experiment.

Results and discussion

Absorption measurements of these two drugs are made separately. Both the drugs showed λ_{\max} at 283.5 nm and for Q.S. the other λ_{\max} was at 331 nm.

The absorbance vs concentration values of C.P. at 283.5 nm and Q.S. at 331 nm are depicted in Table 1 and both showed linear plot.

Table 1. Absorbances of C.P. at 283.5 nm and Q.S. at 283.5 and 331 nm

Concn. ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance of			Q value of Q.S. $A_{331}/A_{283.5}$
	C.P. at 283.5 nm	Q.S. at 283.5 nm	Q.S. at 331 nm	
10	0.033	0.068	0.098	1.49
20	0.065	0.149	0.223	1.49
30	0.103	0.231	0.338	1.46
40	0.141	0.312	0.450	1.44
50	0.176	0.399	0.572	1.43
80	0.304	0.629	0.891	1.41
100	0.369	0.787	1.094	1.39

Note

The absorbances of the mixtures were observed in a spectrophotometer. Since both the drugs showed λ_{max} at 283.5 nm but quinine sulfate at 331 nm only, therefore, the concentration of quinine sulfate is calculated from the absorbance values using the standard graph of quinine sulfate at 331 nm

Table 2. Absorbances of mixtures of C P and Q S at different concentrations

Concn of C P and Q S $\mu\text{g/ml}$ each	Absorbance of mixture at		Concn of Q S at 283.5 nm $\mu\text{g/ml}$	Corrected abs of C P at 283.5 nm	Concn of C P Found
	283.5 nm	331 nm			
24	0.3363	0.265	0.210	0.1262	20.3
32	0.472	0.355	0.2814	0.1905	30.7
40	0.6047	0.445	0.3528	0.2519	40.6
48	0.7375	0.530	0.4202	0.3173	51.1

At 283.5 nm the absorbance is the sum of absorbance values of codeine phosphate and quinine sulfate. The absorbance of quinine sulfate for the experimental concentration as obtained from the standard graph (b) is subtracted from (a) to get the corrected absorbance value of codeine

phosphate (a-b) and corresponding concentrations are obtained from the standard graph as shown in the Table 2

Conclusion

On the basis of our above findings we can conclude that the precision of the method is quite high. Accuracy of the result is highly significant (P.L. 001). The Q value i.e. $A_{331}/A_{283.5}$ for quinine sulfate is estimated to be 1.44 ± 0.05 (for 7 samples) which may be accepted for identification of quinine sulfate.

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References

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- 2 "British Pharmacopoeia", 1993, Vol 1, p 55